

THE EFFECTS OF WITH DIFFERENT PARAMETERS FLUORIDE SURFACE TREATMENT ON THE OSSEINTEGRATION OF IMPLANT MADE OF Ti6Al4V ELI AND MICRO ARC

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to increase the osseointegration by the effect of fluoride ion modification of mikro arc Ti6Al4V Eli Grade 23 surfaces. Mikro ark surfaces coated by electrolysis metod with fluoride. Briefly, six implants were submerged in 1M sodium chloride (NaCl) with 0.2M hydrochloric acid and three different concentrations of hydrofluoric acid (0.001, 0.01, 0.1 vol%). The coating process took place for 20 and 30 min at a constant pH2, a constant temperature of 25°C and constant current of 1mA/cm². Coated materials were controled scanning electron microscopy and X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy. SEM morphological evaluation of the fluoride ion modified surfaces indicated no morphological change from the conventional mikro arc surfaces. Fluoride ion percentages were checked by XPS analysis metod. Additionally, fluoride ion modified implants were placed into medial and distal osteotomies prepared in tibia of white female rabbits. After 21 days, the tibiae were harvested and samples were examined by SEM and XPS. It was observed that the bone-implant contact formed on the fluoride surfaces further than mikro arc surfaces. The mechanism show that by which fluoride ion modification of titanium enhanced osteoblastic differantiation and osseointegration.

1. Introduction

Dental implants are metal post sor frames that are surgically positioned. There are put into the jawbone beneath your gums. After placing, they allow dentist to mount replacement teeth onto them. Generally; metals uses for dental implants are

titanium alloys. The use of titanium as dental implant material is based on the light microscopic observation that bone will heal in close contact to the titanium implant surface [1-3]. The result of this healing has been termed osseointegration by some authors. Terms of osseointegration derived from the Greek and Latin terms for bone and to make whole. However osseointegration is the process that allows dental implants to become a permanent part of your jaw.

Many studies have reported that the bone-implant interface can influence peri-implant bone healing and the osseointegration process [4]. Not only does a rough implant surface ensure an improved bone anchorage when compared to a smooth implant surface, but it also promotes mesenchymal cell differentiation toward an osteoblastic phenotype [5]. Beyond these qualitative conclusions, a temporal argument that bone formation may be modestly accelerated at topographically modified c.p.titanium implants is further suggested. Given the current stronginterest in rapid and immediate loadingof dental implant prostheses, the role of implant surface topography is elevated in significance. The significance of surface chemistry is illustrated by the specific cellular responses to different Ti alloys, to different grades of c.p.titanium, and to Different bulk metals [7,8,9,10]. Some of the newer approaches to changing the reactivity of the c.p.titanium endosseous implant surface include direct chemical modification of titanium surfaces by treatment in simulated body fluid covalent attachment of biological molecules changes in the

surface ion content glow discharge or alkali treatment; to wholesale chemical modification of the titanium or biological grafting with adhesive polymers that can serve to biologically activate the implant surface; as well as alteration of surface hydrophobicity [10,11,12,13,14,15,16]. In these; two assumption are made surface topography. First of all; surface is roughened with micro arc system and bone implant compatibility is increased. After that; surface was chemically modified for increasing osseointegration.

In this study; the effect of fluoride ion modification of micro arc titanium implants on osseointegration as measured animal testing and cell culture assays. It show that; degree of interfacial bone formation following endosseous implant placement in vivo. Fluoride ion treatment of micro arc substrate increases bone to implant contact in the rabbit tibia model.

2. Experimental Procedure

The presence of fluoride (F⁻) ions in the electrolytic environment brings with it an aggressiveness in the attack on titanium. This is due to the formation of complex titanium—fluoride molecules which are very stable and soluble in the electrolyte solution. So that; micro arc titanium surfaces can be coated potassium fluoride with electrolyses metod.

2.1. Titanium dental implant preparation

Titanium implants (3mm diameter x 3 mm long) were machined from c.p. titanium and micro arc etching (Estas Camshaft Industry and Trade inc., Sivas, Turkey).

2.2. Micro arc surfaces preparation

Micro arc oxidation process consists of roughening and micro arc process. At the first stage, the implants are attached to the suspension apparatus made of the same titanium material; It will be chemically roughened at 45-50 ° C with HF acid. In the second stage; In the HF concentrated solution, the products will be given electric currents in the range of 250-300 Amperes at temperatures of 25-30 ° C for 4.5-5 minutes. After the process is completed, rinses will be applied to the implants and cold air will be blown and dried.

2.3. Fluoride Modification Preparation

The fluorine coating process will be completed by applying precipitation in the electrolysis method. Implants with micro arc oxidation applied will be attached to the suspension apparatus made of the

same titanium material and immersed in 5-10-15% concentrated potassium fluoride solutions. Electrolysis process will be performed under 100-130-150 Amperes electric currents for 5-10 minutes at 35 ° C. Since the fluorine coating is laden with potassium minus in the solution, it will occur as a result of adherence of the fluorine charged fluoride to the anode attached to the work piece. As a result, as soon as the electric current starts, potassium and fluoride will chemically separate from each other, and will be covered with samples in the fluoride suspension apparatus.

2.4. SEM/EDS Analyses

Dental implants with surface coating processes will be covered with SEM analysis, coating thickness, surface penetration, adhesion, porosity control, crack control, fluoride release with EDS analysis, and reported. For these procedures, service will be taken from Cumhuriyet University. After the tests of the products are done, the adhesion of the coating to the surface will be checked by mounting on the bone.

2.4. Animals and surgical procedures

Animal tests were performed on coated micro arc and flourine surfaces for determine to osseointegration. The best fluorine oscillation was chosed by us. Six New Zealand white female rabbits, 6 months old and and weighing 3.0-6.5 kg, were used in this in vivo study. Animal tests doing about Sivas Cumhuriyet Universty Ethics Committee Approval with DIN EN 10993 standart. Rabbits were held in cages throught the experimental period. Animal place temperature was regulated at 19±1°C and humidity was 55±10%. The room has a light from 8am-8pm. The implantation consisted in the placement of the flat modified surfaces of Ti implants in direct contact with the cortical bone, flowing a pre-made randomization protocol among to 12 implants; coated to 4 implants 5% fluorine, 4 implants 10% fluorine and last 4 implants 15%. And results show that; fluoride implants improve to osseointegration time.

3. Results and Discussion

Ion-based surface modification processes were ideal candidates to influence osteoblast-material interactions and improve osseointegration time as well, since those could tailor the topographies, surface chemistry and surface energy of the biomaterials. . However, these methods can be done

Figure 1. Micro Arc and Fluoride Surfaces

with simple and cheap applications such as electrolysis. Electrolysis is the passing of a direct electric current through an ionic substance that is either molten or dissolved in a suitable solvent, producing chemical reactions at the electrodes and decomposition of the materials. In this study, we applied this technique to implant potassium fluoride ion into the micro arc surfaces. It could be show that elements of titanium, oxygen, fluorine and carbon were observed on the etching micro arc and modified micro arc surfaces. As with the increase of osseointegration time, the fluorine ossilation signals increased during to animal experiment. The surface fluoride ossilation reached the peak and increasing osseointegration time when percent of fluoride %15. From the SEM/EDS picture before and after fluoride-ion implantation, we observed several evenly dispersed lups formed on the surfaces of the micro arc etching. It didn't show any morphological changes compared to only micro arc surfaces. The implantation of fluoride ions didn't severely effect the crystal lattice of titanium.

Table 1. Chemical Analyses of Micro Arc Etching and Fluoried Surfaces (wt %)

F	Na	Si	P	Cl	K	Total
15.3	6.3	5.2	4.2	69.3	4.1	100

Figure 2. Chemical Analys Graph

Theree main observation have been made with Table 1, Figure 1, and Figure 2. Titanium submitted to electrolyzes modification, even one containing potassium fluoride, merely develops an oxide layer. However, in confined areas where fluoride ions are present, titanium dental implant tested alloys the undergo there is no corrosive process. The continuous presence of fluoride ions in these confined areas. However, one of the typical features of pit and crevice corrosion is the very low circulation of the electrolytic medium. In some very narrow crevices, the electrolyte seeps between two adjacent surfaces and tends to stay there. Fluorine ions thus accumulate on the surface. It can be check with SEM/EDX scanning picture (Figure 1). Currently, to evaluate the biocompatibility of biomaterials, scientists mainly utilize cell

experiments in vitro and animal experiments in vivo. In this study; we applied animals and surgical procedures for observed improved osseointegration time. Results of animal experiments show that, the process of electrolyses of micro arc Ti implants surfaces with the presence of HF at low concentration (5 and 15 weight%) had a positive influence on the osseointegration rate process compared to higher potassium fluoride concentration (15 weight.%) and the absence of potassium fluoride during the surface modification. The reason for such results may come from the conundrum created between specific surface topography combined with complex fluoride-rich surface chemistry.

4. Conclusion

The made of titanium and micro arc surfaces subjected to the implantation of fluoride ions presented the morphologies of homogeneous. The fluorine content of the made of titanium and micro arc surfaces modified layer increased remarkably with the extended implantation time. In comparison with the non-implanted titanium with fluorine, the cells growing on the fluoride-ion-implanted titanium showed the better morphologies, attachment and proliferation. The animal experiments findings confirmed that micro arc etching and fluoride-ion implantation could improve the osseointegration time.

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